

MICROBIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF CHRONIC BACTERIAL PROSTATITIS

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Among inflammatory nonspecific diseases of the genitourinary tract in men, a special place is occupied by chronic bacterial prostatitis, which is a fairly common pathology. Despite the progress achieved in their study and modern approaches to treatment, this problem is becoming increasingly relevant. According to statistics, 40-56% of men of working age are diagnosed with an inflammatory process in the prostate gland, the etiological agents of which are opportunistic microorganisms [43,48, 98].

Numerous studies devoted to the problem of studying chronic inflammatory diseases of the urogenital tract indicate the great difficulty of identifying and topical diagnosis of the inflammatory process in the genitourinary tract in men, especially in the early stages, due to the absence of pathognomonic symptoms [99,46,144,161].

There are various theories about the etiology and pathogenesis of this disease. Data on the etiological agent of CKD are conflicting. Domestic publications state the isolation of gram-positive (*Enterococcus* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp.) cocci from prostate secretions [99]. At the same time, some domestic and most foreign researchers note the predominance of gram-negative (*E. coli*, *Klebsiella* spp., *Proteus* spp.) rods [142]. In this case, in rare cases, attention is paid to the analysis of the structure of the microbial (monoculture, association) landscape [144]. There is no consensus on the diagnostic titer of the pathogen. In most cases, 10⁵ CFU/ml is taken as a diagnostic titer.

However, a number of publications note factors that directly indicate that this liquid in a healthy body is not only sterile, but also bactericidal. The latter is achieved by the presence of a zinc-peptide complex, lysozyme, immunoglobulins and proteolytic enzymes [44].

The lack of data in the available literature on long-term monitoring of the attitude of pathogens of inflammatory diseases of the urogenital tract to antibiotics is probably an important component of the problem of the effectiveness of antibacterial drugs in CKD.

It is known that opportunistic pathogenic microorganisms (OPM) can cause an inflammatory process only in the presence of disturbances in the microbiological and immunological aspects of the body's anti-infective resistance system (CAIR). This indicates that disruption of the relationship between such pathogens and the macroorganism becomes a problem dictating the need for a comprehensive analysis of the results of microbiological and immunological studies of patients. However, in the available literature we have not found data on the study of a set of indicators of the immunological and microbiological aspects of SAIR in patients with inflammatory diseases of the urogenital tract.

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